

Interview - Met Office International Climate Services

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About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

This document describes an interview undertaken as part of the context setting work. You can find a synthesis of all other interviews here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15102198>

Interview: Met Office International Climate Services

Meeting date: 24/02/2025

Joe Daron (Science Manager, International Climate Services at the Met Office)

Joe has a background in meteorology and climate science, but has moved to work engaging with people to co-produce climate services. He has a joint position at the Met Office and University of Bristol with a focus on how climate science and services can be made more useful to wider international context. He works with met services and organisations to build connections to users and translate climate data to those using it e.g. government, industries, public sector etc. An example mentioned was co-production workshops run with the hydropower sector in Nepal - creating narratives/stories of what the future would look like under these scenarios for the specific user group they are working with.

His role also involves understanding decision-making contexts so that services provided are useful for climate change adaptations and climate risks etc. He is particularly interested in African climate services and completed a post-doc in Cape Town. He leads the Weather and Climate Science for Service Partnership (WCSSP) South Africa project.

The Met Office

- ~2000 employees: 500 in science; 150-200 in applied science; 80-100 co-production related work in different contexts; a growing user experience team with a coordinated MO community of practice
- There is both a climate services community of practice and a user engagement community of practice internal to the Met Office. These bring other communities from academic and government partners in through eg. seminars
- UK government “arms length” organisation

- Close relationships to big tech companies on computational side, but also for building value-adding services to the data the MO supplies

Approach to co-production

- Co-production is largely 'business-as-usual' in applied science dept of MO
- User experience team will have different perspective - how MO interact with different people and go about designing data services
- There are parts of MO with a more standard approach to co-production and designing user-centric products. E.g. operational services like the MO app have a more sophisticated approach to UX and taking user feedback to produce better services
- They have internal public weather service representation for external users (e.g. forecasters, aircraft, etc.) who constantly inform development of new services/data visualisations/products based on their needs
- Broadly, two types of services with different approaches:
 - Data driven services - urgency to get the data out there - landscape of people who can do the tailoring e.g. big tech companies
 - User engagement services - dealing with particular groups who need more co-production to understand what they need
 - Big grey area in the middle!

Challenges

- Using the right language: co-creation, co-production, co-exploration etc. The co's - the methods of working together with people to create something
- Representation from user base - they are funded to work on user experience but users aren't funded to trial services and share their experiences. Rely on champions, maybe don't get full representation - need to overcome biases of the people who want to talk.
- International work:
 - Institutional politics, agendas
 - Diversity - reaching out to the most vulnerable communities - only the less vulnerable have the means to communicate/are plugged into institutions
- Openness of co-creation:
 - Not always clear what direction a co-produced project will go in. Causes challenges for funding and timescales, need to be open with the outcome when this is not clear from the start
 - Example: FRACTAL project: <https://www.fractal.org.za/>: engaging in cities in southern Africa to provide climate information, started with what are the problems facing the city, who are relevant people, how are decisions made, took long time to build up trust and didn't end up with much data provision
 - Example: predicting flooding in Mozambique - know that provision of more localised high-res data to address the information deficit is needed. If you

start with the problems then it ends up being about the people - who makes decisions and when, which is much more difficult to measure. Do you consciously not engage in problem space where the data may be relevant and just focus on making it accessible and usable?

- How do you select which products should be co-produced? Based on impact? Based on what the government requests?
- Best practice co-production on resource and time don't always align with specific situations

Similarities to our approach

- Our toolkit is focused on building blocks that people can choose when building their specific services - similar flexible approach to Joe's work
- Co-production for specific audiences is the way we might need to do it for the EDS

Additional reading and contacts

- Presentation mapping UX language to climate services
- Manual for co-production -<https://futureclimateafrica.org/coproduction-manual/> - Africa focused but fairly generic
- IPCC Interactive Atlas - they reached out with feedback survey
- UKCP18 - people whose job is to help with supporting people to access this data
UKCP18 - working group for gov and non-gov for using climate projections
- World Meteorological Organization (WMO) - provides guidance for met services to follow
- Named Met Office Senior Climate Scientist - work in outer hebrides